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D.7.4 Report on IPERION HS training

Lead Author: Rocco Mazzeo

**Co-authors: Silvia Prati, Giorgia Sciutto, Jana Striova, Laura Benassi,
Antonina Chaban**

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Authors (Partner)				
Responsible Author	Name	Rocco Mazzeo	Email	Rocco.mazzeo@unibo.it
	Partner	UNIBO	Phone	+390544037150

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Abstract

The essential aim of Task 7.1 was to provide targeted training to develop suitably skilled individuals and to raise awareness amongst potential users of the benefits of using IPERION HS facilities. To this purpose, two Doctoral Summer Schools (HS-DSS) and two Training Camps (HS-TC) aimed at developing highly skilled professionals in the wider heritage research community, fostering cooperation between the academic community and heritage and research institutions, have been organized.

The HS-DSS and HS-TC activities have been branded and advertised as being part of the IPERION HS Academy for consistency with webinars and other IPERION HS training activities.

The first HS-TC has been organised by CENIEH and took place in Burgos and Atapuerca (Spain) from 11 to 15 July 2021; the second HS-TC has been organised by ITAM-CAS and took place in Telč (Czech Republic) from 26 to 30 July 2023.

The first HS-DSS has been organised by UNIBO-M2ADL and was held, due to the COVID restrictions, online from 13 to 16 July 2021; the second HS-DSS has been organised by ZAG and took place in Ljubljana (Slovenia) from 26 to 30 July 2023.

The HS-DSS mainly reported on successful TNA and JRA achieved during the IPERION-CH project and were addressed to a postgraduate, PhD and post-doc audience. Due to the restrictions raised by the pandemic, only the 2023 edition in Ljubljana (Slovenia) was organised in person. The 2021 edition was completely delivered online.

As the HS-TCs were intended to be more interactive and more appropriate for learners with a mixed educational and professional background, they were both organised in person in 2022 and 2023 respectively.

Both the HS-DSS and HS-TC attracted learners from a wide range of disciplines, so it has been crucial a careful selection of appropriate subject materials and lecturers.

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2 Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
HS	Heritage Science
HS-DSS	IPERION HS Doctoral Summer School
HS-TC	IPERION HS Training Camp
JRA	Joint Research Activity
TNA	Transnational Access
CENIEH	Centro Nacional de Investigacion sobre la Evolucion Humana
ITAM	Institute of Theoretical and Applied Mechanics
ZAG	Slovenian National Building and Civil Engineering Institute
UNIBO-M2ADL	University of Bologna – Microchemistry and Microscopy Art Diagnostic Laboratory

3 Narrative (technical) description

3.1 Introduction

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As the HS-TCs were intended to be more interactive and more appropriate for learners with a mixed educational and professional background, they were both organised in person in 2022 and 2023 respectively.

Both the HS-DSS and HS-TC attracted learners from a wide range of disciplines, so it has been crucial a careful selection of appropriate subject materials and lecturers.

3.2 Description of the Training Activities

3.2.1 1st HS-TC Burgos, 2022

The first HS-TC has been organised by CENIEH and took place in Burgos and Atapuerca (Spain) from 11 to 15 July 2022. This HS TC was aimed at promoting the involvement of new heritage science communities and, therefore, the subject dealt with ***Paleontological and paleoanthropological heritage***. Cutting-edge tools for materials characterisation and dating applied to Paleontological and Paleoanthropological heritage were presented and discussed with an international audience of 25 participants. The HS TC was structured in a five-day intensive hands-on experience, laboratory analyses, group projects, general lectures, and fieldwork sessions. With innovative mobile and laboratory equipment, best practices and methodological approaches have been transferred directly to the participants as new potential users of the TNA activities.

Moreover, it has been an excellent opportunity for a hands-on experience in the functioning, use and applications of the FIXLAB facilities offered by CENIEH within IPERION HS.

During the five intensive days of lectures and hands-on experience based on a problem-solving approach, trainees learned how to use different methodologies to delve into the most relevant

dating techniques (Electron Spin Resonance, Optically Stimulated Luminescence, Paleomagnetism, Uranium series) and materials characterization (nano and micro-computed tomography). Table 1 reports some figures related to the 1st HS-TC in Burgos.

Number of participants	26 [10 countries of affiliation (16 nationalities)]
Participant degree/position	9 postgraduate, 9 PhD students, 3 post-doc, 1 practitioner, 4 other
Average satisfaction	9.62*
Practical information on how to apply, %	Average 9.52*
Organization & timing, %	Average 8.88*
Quality of theory sessions, %	Average 9.76*
Quality of practical sessions, %	Average 9.44*

*Scale: 1=very poor to 10=excellent

Training Camp #1 (2022): PARTICIPANTS

10 countries of affiliation (16 nationalities)

Figure 1 Geography of 1st HS-TC participants

Figure 2 Practical sessions at CENIEH labs, Day 3 at 1st HS-TC in Burgos

Figure 3 Atapuerca on-site visit, Day 4 at 1st HS-TC in Burgos

Training Camp #1 (2022): survey results

HSAcademy

Question 6: Any further comments? What did you like most/least?

- I find the course was exactly as advertised. I have no complaints. I am very happy and satisfied with how the course turned out
- Most - Atapuerca; least - too little time for such amount of information. There should be more days at Atapuerca;
- The entire day of theory sessions was maybe too much for one day (maybe half day of theory, and the other one practical) like day one. For the rest, it was perfect!
- Lab visits, practical sessions and field sessions incredible experiences that I never expected and experienced before. This is a lifetime experience. I am happy, satisfied and thankful for having this opportunity!
- The most exciting part of the workshops were the visit to Atapuerca site and the case studies and the labs. For improvement, I would suggest unloading the daily schedule so that we do not rush between the different activities and enjoy each of them
- Perhaps more practical sessions, where we are in smaller groups, to experience practical aspects. I do understand this would require more time though. Excellent experience and very well organized. Thank you!

T8.2 Integrating access to training activities

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Figure 4 Extract of comments from the anonymous post-event survey by participants of 1st HS-TC

3.2.2 2nd HS-TC Telč, 2023

The 2nd HS-TC has been organised by ITAM and took place in Telč (Czech Republic) from 26 to 30 June 2023. The 2nd Training Camp offered an experience with the complexity of **built heritage** and introduced the cutting-edge tools for diagnostics and methods of investigation applied to it. During the five intensive days of lectures and hands-on experience based on a problem-solving approach, trainees learned how to apply selected advanced diagnostic and documentation methods, how to approach the protection of built heritage and how to experimentally verify and monitor the effects of climatic phenomena on built heritage. It lasted 5 days and has been structured in general lectures and hands-on activities on specific case studies, including fieldwork sessions and laboratory experiments. The case studies have been addressed in smaller interdisciplinary groups. The training foresaw direct interaction with the reference expert scientist for each technique/method, encouraging thorough discussions and contributive debate among participants.

Table 2 reports some figures related to the 2nd HS-TC in Telč.

Number of participants	17 (10 countries of residence)
Participant degree/position	8 postgraduate, 6 PhD students, 2 post-doc, 1 practitioner
Average satisfaction	8.82*
Practical information on how to apply, %	Average 8.18*
Organization & timing, %	Average 9.35*
Quality of theory sessions, %	Average 8.71*
Quality of practical sessions, %	Average 8.47*
Table 2	

*Scale: 1=very poor to 10=excellent

Training Camp #2 (2023): 17 PARTICIPANTS 10 countries of affiliation

Figure 5 Geography of 2nd HS-TC participants

Figure 6 Theory sessions of 1st HS-TC at ITAM CAS in Telč

Figure 7 Practical sessions of 2nd HS-TC at the laboratories of ITAM CAS in Telč

Figure 8 Delivery of attendance certificate to 2nd HS-TC participants

3.2.3 1st HS-DSS Bologna (online), 2021

The 1st HS-DSS has been organised by UNIBO-M2ADL and took place online from 13 to 16 July 2021. The 1st HS-DSS was aimed at providing examples of *excellence in heritage science for conservation and collection care research and access*.

Due to the pandemic restrictions, it has been decided to deliver the HS-DSS *completely online* and comprised of four intensive days of lectures and virtual study visits, during which participants became acquainted with the multidisciplinary skills of the IPERION HS consortium and knowledge accumulated by the partners. Lectures and virtual study tours have been adapted to an interdisciplinary audience of learners by focusing more on problem-solving approaches than on the specific adopted scientific methods/techniques.

The 1st HS-DSS was opened to postgraduate, PhD students, post-docs and practitioners, in particular, early career researchers involved in heritage science studies and was particularly aimed at potential users of the IPERION HS trans-national access (TNA) program. Participants have been made acquainted with the importance of being able to access to large and medium-scale facilities, mobile laboratories and data archives within a European dimension.

Table 3 reports some figures related to the 1st HS-DSS organised online by UNIBO-M2ADL

Number of participants	190
Participant degree/position	50 postgraduate, 97 PhD students, 27 post-doc, 11 practitioner, 5 other
Average satisfaction	8.61*
Practical information on how to apply, %	Average 8.18*
Organization & timing, %	Average 8.09*
Quality of theory sessions, %	Average 8.34*
Table 3	

*Scale: 1=very poor to 10=excellent

Doctoral Summer School

DSS participants by country

Figure 9 Geography of 2nd HS-DSS participants (online)

Doctoral Summer School

Q5 Please provide any comments or suggestions

- I really enjoyed the school. It was a very fruitful opportunity to learn and to deep some topics for me less-known. Just to leave a suggestion, as my interest and specialization is mostly directed towards textile materials, I missed only more analytical applications on these materials, usually overlooked. Tahnks again for the wonderful organization. I hope to attend more IPERION initiative like this one!
- It was a very interesting and inspirational course. I appreciate if you could share more information about how to join a group which are currently investigating (if it exists), because some of us are emerging conservators who are not supported jet by a research group or need more experience on scientific conservation before starting our own research. Thank you very much for this seminary and congratulations to all the organizers and lecturers for their research.
- Problem with logging into the program - application form (not working, inserting CV, etc.) An otherwise inspiring online conference. **(solved already during registration)**
- Congratulations to Prof. Mazzeo and all the team involved in the DSS. The lectures were all very highly qualified in terms of scientific quality and they represent the state of art in the broad transdisciplinary field of Heritage Science. Despite some very few normal difficulties faced by any scientific event (not only online ones), everything was just fine. The only suggestion I would make for future schools intended to have online sessions would be considering mainly afternoon sessions (CET time) in order to facilitate participation of very "easterns or westerns". I do hope we continue collaborating with Iperion and E-RIHS in the fields of scientific education and dissemination, through our Brazilian National Association ANTECIPA. Thank you very much.

Figure 10 Extract of comments from the anonymous post-event survey by participants of 1st HS-DSS

3.2.4 2nd HS-DSS Ljubljana, 2023

The 2nd HS-DSS has been organised by ZAG and took place in Ljubljana from 17 to 21 July 2023. The 2nd HS-DSS was aimed at providing examples of excellence in heritage science in the **environmental impact on built heritage and its digitalization**. The HS-DSS comprised four intensive

days of lectures, during which participants became acquainted with the multidisciplinary skills of the IPERION HS consortium and the knowledge accumulated by the partners.

Issues such as materials and procedures for low environmental impacts, new methods for the preservation of buildings and structures, digitalization and social and economic impacts have been taught to participants.

Lectures and study tours have been adapted to an interdisciplinary audience of learners by focusing more on problem-solving than on the specific adopted scientific methods/techniques.

The 2nd HS-DSS was opened to postgraduate, PhD students, post-docs and practitioners, in particular early career researchers involved in heritage science studies on built heritage.

HS-DSS was particularly aimed at potential users of the IPERION HS trans-national access (TNA) program. They will understand the importance of being able to access to large and medium-scale facilities, mobile laboratories, and data archives within a European dimension.

Table 4 reports some figures related to the 2nd HS-DSS organised by ZAG.

Number of participants	21
Participant degree/position	3 postgraduate, 11 PhD students, 3 post-doc, 4 other
Average satisfaction	8.74*
Practical information on how to apply, %	Average 8.85*
Organization & timing, %	Average 8.00*
Quality of theory sessions, %	Average 8.52*
Table 4	

*Scale: 1=very poor to 10=excellent

Doctoral Summer School #2 (2023): 21 PARTICIPANTS

11 countries of residence

Figure 11 Geography of HS-DSS 2 participants

Lectures at 2nd HS-DSS at ZAG, Ljubljana (Slovenia)

Sitarjevec on-site visit at 2nd HS-DSS, ZAG, Ljubljana (Slovenia)

Participants of the 2nd HS-DSS at ZAG, Ljubljana, Slovenia

4 Conclusion

The KPIs indicators (KPI1, KPI2, KPI3 and KPI4) as described and agreed in deliverable D7.1 were all met. In particular, the training events have been organised in the way they were originally planned apart from the fact that the 1st HS-DSS has been completely taught online because of the pandemic restrictions. Moreover, both the support quality, the efficiency of the TC and DSS user outreach and the quality of the delivered training in all cases got positive satisfaction from more than 90% of the survey participants.

The 4 training events involved a total of 254 participants from many European and extra-UE countries. 86% of the 43 participants of the HS-TCs were holding post-doc, post-graduate, or PhD degrees and only 14% of them were practitioners or others. Given the particular aim of the TCs that foresee hands-on and problem-solving activities, the participation of practitioners should be increased in the organisation of future training events as the taught materials and knowledge need to be better disseminated among professionals involved in conservation practice.

As expected, 91% of learners participating in the HS-DSSs were holding post-doc, post-graduate or PhD degrees and only 9% of them were practitioners or others. In this case, the majority (51%) was holding PhD degrees. This percentage is higher than the one measured for HS-TCs where the participants holding a PhD were just 35%. This result is perfectly in line with the aim of the HS-DSS which was meant to be the place where the results of the advanced research carried out by the IPERION-HS partners were presented and discussed.

The lesson learned from the organisation of the online HS-DSS organised by UNIBO-M2ADL is quite relevant as it has been possible to reach a very large audience if compared with the 2nd in presence of HS-DSS held in Ljubljana. At the time of COVID, its organisation was quite challenging and, despite the important results achieved in terms of the number of participants, it has to be underlined the constraint raised by some participants concerning a certain lack of interactions between them and lecturers.